

Deliverable 3.2.1.1

PROCESS FOR CONTRIBUTING AND ACCESSING FAIR DATA
DEFINED AND EXECUTED WITH INDUSTRY PARTNERS
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D3.2.1.1 Process for contributing and accessing FAIR data defined and executed with industry partners

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Table of Contents

General Information	4
Summary	4
Deliverable within NFDI4Energy.....	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Process for contributing and accessing FAIR data	5
2.1 FAIR Principle.....	5
2.2 Requirements	6
2.3 Process for contributing FAIR data.....	7
2.4 Process for accessing FAIR data	8
2.5 Toolbox.....	9
2.6 NFDI4Energy data sharing services	10
2.7 Self-Assessment Tool.....	11
3. Conclusion.....	13
References.....	14
List of figures	14

General Information

Summary

The deliverable D3.2.1.1 proposes a defined process for contributing and accessing FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data within the energy sector, based on the services from NFDI4Energy, in collaboration with industry partners. It emphasizes the need for data sharing services due to the dispersed nature of energy-related datasets across stakeholders. A major focus is involving industry to ensure real-world relevance and compliance, facilitating mutual contribution and usage of data.

In this deliverable, we first summarize the established FAIR principles and identify key requirements such as ensuring data quality, managing legal and ethical constraints, and addressing technical challenges. Building on these principles, the deliverable presents the process for contributing and accessing FAIR data, leveraging services from NFDI4Energy and engaging industry partners.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

Figure 1- Task Area 3 connections to other Task Areas within the NFDI4Energy consortium

The diagram shows how Task Area 3 involves industry partners. M3.1 gathers industry requirements, which leads to two main tasks: T3.2.1 creates processes for sharing FAIR data, and T3.2.2 handles community services. M3.3 provides substitute data when needed. Technical support and services are provided from other related TAs. Specifically, TA4 supports the implementation of domain ontologies, metadata standards, and the metadata registry, ensuring that data are well-structured, interoperable, and reusable.

1. Introduction

NFDI4Energy is a consortium within the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) that aims at developing an open ecosystem for FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) research assets in interdisciplinary energy systems research. Data in energy domain dispersed currently across various stakeholders, such as utilities, grid operators and consumers. Data sharing services can be used to overcome these challenges and provide a common space for collecting, processing, and sharing energy-related data among different actors[6].

To create effective data-sharing services, it is important to engage the industry in the development process. This is because industry participation serves as a key element for the successful establishment of community services in energy system research. Industry partners can not only contribute important technical and business datasets, but also as users to access existing data and services provided by NFDI4Energy. Therefore, the aim of Task Area (TA) 3 is to include the industry in the development process. The following targets are set to be achieved by TA 3:

- Identify and involve industry partners and gather their requirements for service adoption
- Develop clear processes to actively involve industry partners in services development
- Identify requirements for substituting data and implement a set of tools to generate synthetic data as well as anonymised data

As one part of TA3, Task 3.2 involves establishing clear guidelines for how new data can be shared while ensuring compliance with the technical requirements defined by TA4. This includes specifying necessary data formats, standards, and metadata that describe the contents of the datasets, as well as outlining any licenses required for their usage. Additionally, Task 3.2 integrates the requirements gathered from industry partners in M3.1 within TA4 and facilitate a validation process to ensure ongoing improvements to the data-sharing framework.

To present this part of the work, this deliverable is divided into the following sections: Firstly, the meaning of FAIR principles is clarified in section 2.1 FAIR Principle. The requirements from industry partners are pointed out as section 2.2 Requirements. Based on these, section 2.3 Process for contributing FAIR data and 2.4 Process for accessing FAIR data are outlined. Additionally, tools that may be utilized throughout the overall process are mentioned in section 2.5 Toolbox. In section 2.7 Self-Assessment Tool is used to assess how FAIR of a dataset is.

2. Process for contributing and accessing FAIR data

2.1 FAIR Principle

According to [7], the FAIR principles provide guidelines to improve the management and accessibility of data. They are structured around four key aspects:

- Findability

To ensure findability in the FAIR Principles, data and metadata should be assigned a unique and persistent identifier, such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) or Uniform Resource Locator (URL), for long-term accessibility. The data must be accompanied by rich metadata, which includes the data identifier and enhances searchability. Both data and metadata should be indexed in searchable resources, enabling easy discovery by humans and machines.

- Accessibility

In terms of accessibility in the FAIR Principles, data and metadata must be retrievable via their identifier using a standardized, open, and universally implementable protocol. This protocol should

also allow for authentication and authorization when required. Furthermore, metadata should remain accessible even if the data is no longer available, ensuring continued transparency and usability.

- Interoperability

For interoperability in the FAIR Principles, data and metadata should be represented using a formal and widely accessible language. They should also adopt vocabularies that comply with FAIR principles and include qualified references to other relevant data, enabling smooth integration and compatibility across different systems and datasets.

- Reusability

Data and metadata should be thoroughly described with precise and relevant attributes. They should also meet domain-specific community standards to support future use.

2.2 Requirements

Considering the range of diverse data involved in the energy sector, such as consumption patterns, generation metrics from renewable sources, and grid performance statistics, it is essential to develop a framework for data management. By ensuring that data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, such services enable industry partners to easily locate relevant datasets, integrate diverse information sources, and leverage insights for innovative solutions in areas like energy efficiency and sustainability. However, there are still some requirements that need to be met. In Task 3.1, we focus on identifying and engaging industry partners to gather their requirements, ensuring that the services align with real-world needs. What's more, Task 3.3 involves designing a survey to further requirements, specifically for substituting data. Based on these results and in [4][5], some requirements in terms of open data in the energy sector are as follows:

- Ethical and Security Concerns

In the energy sector, data often includes sensitive information related to user behaviour, consumption patterns, and preferences. It is crucial to handle this data responsibly to protect privacy and ensure robust data security measures are in place.

- Ensuring Data Quality

The accuracy of energy-related research heavily relies on high-quality data. There is a risk that data providers may supply incomplete, inaccurate, inconsistent, or outdated datasets, which can undermine research quality and efficiency in areas such as demand forecasting or renewable energy integration. Implementing rigorous processes to verify and maintain data quality is essential for reliable analyses.

- Legal Restrictions

Energy providers may be subject to various legal regulations governing the release of data, particularly concerning proprietary information or consumer privacy laws. These restrictions can limit access to critical datasets needed for research on energy efficiency, sustainability initiatives, or market analysis.

- Technical Challenges

Data in the energy sector may be provided in formats and standards that do not align with user requirements, complicating access and processing for applications like smart grid management or

real-time analytics. Ensuring that all provided data is machine-readable, well-structured, and easily accessible is vital for facilitating effective use by researchers and practitioners.

- Coordination of Different Interests

The energy sector involves a diverse range of stakeholders—including policymakers, researchers, utility companies, and consumers—each with their own perspectives and objectives. Harmonizing these differing interests to establish common guidelines for data sharing can be challenging but necessary for fostering collaboration.

- Handling Missing Values

Addressing missing values in datasets related to energy consumption or production is critical for accurate modelling and analysis. Strategies must be developed to either impute missing values or provide clear documentation on their absence.

- Management of Personal Data

Given the sensitivity of personal consumption information in the energy sector, careful management practices are required to comply with privacy regulations while still enabling valuable insights into trends such as peak usage times or behavioural responses to pricing changes.

2.3 Process for contributing FAIR data

Considering that the core objective of the FAIR principles is to enhance the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data, along with the increasing demand for data sharing and transparency in energy domain, the process for contributing FAIR data is as shown in Figure 2 Process for contributing FAIR data. To make the process clearer, we use different coloured boxes: the blue box indicates that the user is responsible for data preparation, the green box shows that the admin handles those steps, and the grey box represents areas where both the admin and user can work together. The description for each step is as follows:

- Data Preparation

In this step, the user can collect and prepare the data they want to upload, such as energy consumption data and market data.

- Access Mechanism

Once the user has prepared the data, it moves to the Access Mechanism, which is managed by the admin. In this step, the admin configures and enforces access control policies to ensure data security and compliance.

- Data Registry

The data is officially registered in this step.

- Legal Conditions Check

This step involves verifying adherence to data protection laws, privacy policies, and institutional guidelines to prevent legal risks and ensure ethical data handling.

- Anonymization Framework

Based on the result from previous step and requirements, anonymization techniques are applied to protect sensitive information.

- Metadata Management

This process involves collecting relevant metadata, such as data format, source, timestamp.

- Metadata Retrieval

To facilitate quick search and retrieval of metadata, efficient storage and indexing mechanisms need to be designed. This process may involve database queries, API calls, or search engine-based indexing.

- Data Provenance Information

The process includes recording the source, transformation history, and processing steps of the data, along with any factors that may affect its quality.

- Data Integrity and Validation

To ensure data quality, the data will be validated, such as by checking its accuracy, consistency, completeness, and validity.

- Robust Data Archiving and Preservation

The process ensures that data is stored in a way that it remains accessible when needed, while also protecting it from unauthorised access or loss.

Figure 2 Process for contributing FAIR data

2.4 Process for accessing FAIR data

Another part of this submission focuses on the process of accessing FAIR data, as shown in Figure 3 Process for accessing FAIR data, which is divided into the following steps:

- Data Search

This step involves implementing a comprehensive search functionality that allows users to efficiently locate datasets. Users should be able to search using various parameters such as keywords, metadata, or data attributes.

- Access Mechanism

The access mechanism defines the process by which users can request and obtain the datasets they need. The mechanism should also support different access methods such as direct downloads and API access.

- Data Visualization

Data visualization is crucial for presenting complex datasets in an understandable and actionable way. This step involves providing tools for users to create visual representations of the data, such as graphs or charts.

- Multi-Format Data

This step ensures that the services support multiple data formats to accommodate diverse user needs. It includes the ability to handle different types of data (e.g., CSV, JSON, XML, etc.) and ensure seamless integration across various systems.

Figure 3 Process for accessing FAIR data

2.5 Toolbox

In this section, we have come up with a variety of potential tools that could be employed in line with the processes. The introduction about tools and connection with requirements are described as follows:

- Application Programming Interface (API)

An API is a set of rules and protocols that define how software components interact with each other. It allows different software systems to communicate, facilitating data exchange and integration of functionalities.

In the context of data search, APIs can be utilized to access and retrieve specific datasets or information. For example, by calling an API from a data provider, users can quickly obtain the required data without manually searching for it. This approach not only enhances efficiency but also enables real-time access to the most up-to-date information. Additionally, APIs can support various query parameters, allowing users to customize search results based on their specific needs, leading to more flexible and precise data retrieval.

- Data Visualization Tool

Data Visualization Tools are software applications that assist users in converting raw data into visual representations, such as charts, graphs, and dashboards. These tools enable users to easily analyse complex datasets and uncover trends, patterns, and anomalies that may not be readily visible in textual formats.

- Data Format Converter

A Data Format Converter is a software application designed to transform data from one format to another, enabling compatibility and interoperability between various systems and applications. In an increasingly data-centric world, organizations often encounter multiple data sources and formats, such as CSV, JSON, XML, among others.

Databases typically store data in specific formats optimized for efficient storage and retrieval. However, when users need to analyse or share this data across different services, it may be

necessary to convert it into a certain required format. A Data Format Converter can simplify this process by allowing users to select the format of data while upload and download.

- Metadata Schema

A Metadata Schema is a structured framework that defines the organization, format, and semantics of metadata within a dataset. It provides a standardized way to describe the content, context, and structure of data, making it easier for users to understand and utilize datasets effectively. In the context of a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) service, a well-defined Metadata Schema is essential for ensuring that data adheres to the FAIR principles. It enables datasets to be easily discoverable and accessible while facilitating interoperability among different systems.

For users, having access to a comprehensive Metadata Schema enhances their ability to find relevant data quickly and understand its context and applicability. This leads to more informed decision-making based on accurate information. For administrators, implementing a Metadata Schema is important for maintaining data quality and consistency. It helps in managing datasets effectively and ensures compliance with standards required for data sharing and reuse.

- Documentation

Since it is important to involve industry partners, who are potential users, guidelines serve as a valuable tool in this process. These guidelines can offer a comprehensive introduction to services, such as the Data Format Converter, thereby assisting users in becoming familiar with the workflow.

2.6 NFDI4Energy data sharing services

Based on the tools identified in the previous section, we compare the existing services e.g. Open Energy Platform (OEP)[3] and Leibniz Data Manager (LDM)[2], with some features as shown in Table 1.

OEP is a collaborative versioned dataset repository specifically designed for storing and sharing open energy system model datasets. The platform provides automated data visualizations and API access, making energy research data easily accessible to the scientific community[3]. LDM is an open-source web-based application for research data management that uses semantic web technologies and knowledge graphs[2]. While existing services from OEP and LDM provide valuable foundations, neither fully encompasses the comprehensive toolset outlined earlier. For instance, these two existing services do not include a data format converter. Another important point is that conditional data sharing is currently not supported. In cases involving personal data, there is no clear explanation of how this data will be handled or used.

Table 1 Comparison of Required Features with Existing Services

Required Feature	LDM	OEP
Legal Conditions Check	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Privacy Statement is available • Complex legal checks are hard to do. Users choose a suitable license when uploading data. 	Data Privacy Statement is available
User Registration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No open registration for external users • Registration requires administrative approval 	Account creation through email verification

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Login with ORCID ID supported • IDM service integration planned 	
User Classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Must initially belong to an organization • Can create sub-organizations 	Organizations and groups exist
Conditional Data Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group/organization not yet designed for conditional sharing • Can be implemented when required by projects • Will be discussed with industry partners through workshops/surveys 	License under reuseable data in the metadata.
Data Contribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For organizations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Member – can see the organization’s private datasets Editor – can edit and publish datasets Admin – can add, remove and change roles for organization members • For groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Member – can add/remove datasets from groups Admin – can edit group information, as well as manage group’s members • Supports multiple formats (CSV, JSON, XML) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-registered: Browse and download open data • Registered: Create/edit database entries • Supports multiple formats (CSV, JSON, XSL)
Metadata Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata available • Extra requirements about metadata can be added, e.g. edit metadata 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manually creating OEMetadata using the OpenMetadataIntegration (OMI) • Creating OEMetadata using the OEMetaBuilder • Migrated to OEMetadata 2.0
Data Visualization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Visualisation available (2D/3D visualization) • Datasets Comparison 	Data Upload Preview
Documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LDM Demo Video 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Energy Academy (OEA) courses • Tutorials for OEF tools
API Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • API available • Users can create API tokens 	Upload and download can via API
Connection with other Services	Simulation features considered	Not defined
Primary Use Case	Publishing finalized data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Database for sharing and storing data • Scenario bundle

2.7 Self-Assessment Tool

To evaluate the process of accessing and uploading FAIR data, we used the FAIR data self-assessment tool provided by the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC). This tool is designed to help researchers assess the "FAIRness" of their data by guiding them through a set of 12 questions, divided

into four sections corresponding to the FAIR principles: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability[1].

Findable

Q1: Does the dataset have any identifiers assigned?

Data registry and metadata management are crucial in the process of data contribution. We aim to achieve globally unique, citable, and persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI, Persistent Uniform Resource Locator (PURL), or Handle), while also considering the use of local identifiers.

Q2: Is the dataset identifier included in all metadata records/files describing the data?

Through effective metadata management, it is indeed possible to ensure that dataset identifiers are consistently included in all relevant metadata records.

Q3: How is the data described by a metadata record?

The data described by a metadata record is structured according to a specific metadata schema, which provides a standardized framework for organizing and representing information about the dataset. A metadata schema defines the elements, attributes, and relationships that should be included in the metadata records, ensuring consistency and interoperability across different datasets. The information about metadata schema will be reviewed from TA 4.

Q4: What type of searchable repository or registry is the metadata record in?

To this part, data is held in one place, and the metadata record is searchable through several registries.

Accessible

Q5: How accessible is the data?

The accessibility of the data is influenced by a defined process that includes key components such as a Legal Conditions Check and an Anonymization Framework. In this way, the entire dataset is accessible to persons who meet certain conditions.

Q6: Is the data available online once access has been approved?

The APIs provide a standardized way for users to retrieve and interact with the datasets in a programmatic manner. However, the exact API that will be used for accessing the data will need to be specified later. This allows for flexibility in integrating different types of data sources and ensuring that users can efficiently obtain the information they need.

Q7: Will the metadata record be available even if the data is no longer available?

We are currently unsure whether the metadata record will remain accessible even if the associated data is no longer available.

Interoperable

Q8: What (file) format(s) is the data available in?

The data is available in multiple formats, which allows for greater flexibility and usability. For instance, the TA1 Data format-converter can be utilized to convert data into various file formats as needed.

Q9: What best describes the types of vocabularies used to describe/define the data elements?

We are currently uncertain about the specific types of vocabularies employed to describe or define the data elements, as the data is primarily sourced from industrial partners.

Q10: How is the relationship to other data and resources described in the metadata?

The relationship to other data and resources is articulated in the metadata through robust metadata management, particularly by employing the TA4 metadata schema.

Reusable

Q11: Which of the following best describes the licence/usage rights assigned to the data and included in the metadata record?

The license and usage rights assigned to the data, as included in the metadata record, are currently uncertain. This uncertainty arises from the need for legal conditions check, which is essential to ensure compliance with relevant regulations and agreements. Additionally, we may need to refer to the TA4 Common Ontology and Metadata Schema for further clarification on how these aspects are documented.

Q12: How much provenance information has been captured to facilitate data reuse?

Through metadata management, detailed provenance information can be documented, including aspects such as the origin of the data, the processes involved in its collection and transformation, and any modifications made over time.

This tool will generate a FAIR score based on the provided responses. At present, the score stands at 88%, with key areas for improvement being Accessibility related to metadata records and Reusability in terms of the extent of provenance information captured to support data reuse. We recognize that there is room for enhancement in these areas. To address this, we will enhance collaboration across various task areas to improve the overall process.

3. Conclusion

The NFDI4Energy services provide a solution for managing energy sector data by following FAIR principles. Through organized data structures, clear naming conventions, and effective search tools, the services make it easier for energy professionals to find and use the information they need.

The deliverable about defined process for contributing and accessing is based on existing information from industrial partners and different task areas in the project. Due to the current development stage of the service, the elements required in the defined process, for instance API and Metadata schema, are still subject to adjustments and refinement. Other NFDI services, such as from NFDI4Chem, have been referenced. NFDI4Chem provides valuable insights, including well-structured data management strategies, interoperability between different research data repositories, and robust standards for data sharing and reuse. What's more, the existing services from OEP and LDM serve as useful references for enhancing our services' design and functionality. For these reasons, we propose to collect feedback from the industry based on the current data sharing and accessing process. Building on this, we will refine the process by addressing the requirements for substitute data as identified in M3.3. The detailed specifications will be described in D3.1.2.2 Data Sharing Guidelines and further integrated into LDM.

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List of figures

Figure 1 Process for contributing FAIR data.....	8
Figure 2 Process for accessing FAIR data	9